

Resilience topics included in the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme: Current work and future opportunities

Karla Cervantes Barron^a, Francesco Gardumi^b, Raghav Pant^c, Jennifer Cronin^d, Julia Tomei^d, Alex Kell^e, Jonathan M Cullen^a

a Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom

b Department of Energy Technology, Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan, Sweden

c University of Oxford, United Kingdom

d University College London, United Kingdom

e Imperial College London, United Kingdom

This work is licensed under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) International License.

Cite as: K. Cervantes Barron, F. Gardumi, R. Pant, J. Tomei, J. Cronin, A. Kell, 'Resilience topics included in the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme: Current work and future opportunities', Climate Compatible Growth, 2022.

DOI: <https://zenodo.org/record/6445238>

Abstract

There are several definitions and applications of the concept of resilience. In climate change mitigation and adaptation, resilience can refer to the transformation of systems to cope with external shocks. The Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme offers opportunities to improve the resilience of energy, transport systems and other biophysical systems linked to them. Different CCG workstreams (WSs) and models are involved in each topic. This document seeks to identify the resilience topics involved in the CCG offer, make clear links between WSs and models that partner countries may use, identify collaborative opportunities for the different models and workstreams to answer more resilience questions, and identify gaps for future work.

Keywords

Resilience; Shock; Infrastructure; Energy system; Supply chain; Materials; Food; Water; CCG

1. Introduction

Climate change is causing shocks that affect several biophysical systems at once, including energy and material resources, water, land, or ecosystems. To cope with such shocks, the practice of resilience may be introduced in the systems involved. While there are several definitions of resilience, one definition that is relevant to the work of the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme comes from the UK National Infrastructure Commission [1], which states that "resilience involves actions that help infrastructure to anticipate, resist, absorb, recover, adapt and transform in response to external shocks". Policy needs to consider measures that increase resilience across all the domains involved. Policy coherence becomes imperative and it can be supported by modelling tools that analyse mutual impacts between systems under conditions of climatic changes.

For the energy system, shocks of particular interest include: gradual climate change affecting renewable resources and the operations of thermal power stations, increasingly frequent and severe extreme weather events, oil and/or gas price spikes (particularly relevant on the national scale and if the country has a large reliance on imported commodities), or changes in demands. The desire to increase resilience against these potential shocks can lead planners to pursue actions such as reducing reliance on fuel imports by increasing domestic fuel extraction or renewable generation, reducing reliance on (large) hydropower by developing a more diverse technology mix for electricity generation, or investing in transmission infrastructure to reduce vulnerability to storms.

There are potential shocks to systems beyond the energy system (e.g., land and water) that could have important effects on the energy system. For example, severe droughts or flooding events could cause abrupt changes in the water and food supply chains (e.g., switching the operation of dams to a flood-safe and irrigation-first fashion), with cascaded effects on the energy sector. Such examples show that resilience must be increased in a range of planning domains that goes beyond the energy sector. Coherent policy making across several domains (such as climate, land, energy and water) that centres resilience is needed for countries to deliver on the 2030 Agenda (e.g., SDGs 2, 6, 7, 13 and 15) while minimising the trade-offs between the goals.

The CCG programme aims to support investment in sustainable energy and transport systems to meet development priorities in the Global South. The programme is providing research and public goods to help countries develop economic strategies, plans, and policies to attract investment into low-carbon growth opportunities across multiple sectors. The concept of resilient infrastructure is often associated with *adaptation* to climate change. But resilience should be embedded in all development and climate mitigation actions for ensuring a climate-change-ready global low carbon system of energy and other infrastructure is developed, i.e., this is another strand of climate compatibility.

Long-term planning for low-carbon strategies should be integrated with an understanding of underlying climate stressors and risks that might affect the existing and future investments into infrastructures. Infrastructures can lock-in development for several years and if investments are made in locations which are vulnerable to climate hazards, then it could deter sustainable development.

Energy system and wider development planning needs to consider resilience at several scales (with short-term operational resilience feeding into long-term planning decisions) and across several domains (with an integrated perspective on energy system and transportation planning, as well as resource use). Planning of the energy and transportation system also has consequences on other biophysical systems (e.g., water, land, and ecosystems), while a lack of policy coherence can bear severe long-term consequences across systems. For example, planning the building of large-scale hydropower infrastructure without taking into account climatic changes could have consequences on: 1) electricity supply security in the short-term (due to draughts or floods) and in the long-term (the long-living assets could become stranded with trends of decreasing water availability); 2) climate mitigation; 3) agricultural practices; 4) clean water supply. Long-term planning should also include the consideration of how demand for different materials (e.g., lithium for batteries) could rise due to the transition to low-carbon systems. If the carbon emissions associated with these materials and infrastructure are limited from the start, then higher emission savings can be achieved.

1.1. Scope and structure of the document

This document details how resilience is currently addressed in CCG modelling tools, and develops a set of steps and recommendations for how these tools can be used together and combined further for improved resilience studies. The elements include: long-term infrastructure assessment and infrastructure planning; spatially detailed climate hazard and infrastructure networks; material resource uses; land use and water use impacts of the energy and transportation systems.

The team working on this document was multi-disciplinary, aiming to analyse how modelling tools traditionally used to model each aspect of resilience separately can be soft-linked, to provide insights for comprehensive resilience planning. The following tools that are part of the CCG modelling toolkit are considered in this document: OSemOSYS [2]–[4] and FLEXTOOL [5] (looking at energy systems optimisation and planning), MUSE [6], [7] (also analysing the energy system, but with an agent-based perspective), NISMOD [8] (focussing on the resilience of infrastructure), MAT-dp [9] (assessing material requirements for energy infrastructure) and CLEWs [10] (jointly optimising the resource use and investments across the energy, land use and water systems). The sections below detail the results, i.e. they map the potential links. The linking of the tools marks a step ahead in research practice by breaking siloes of modelling practice and combining aspects often analysed in parallel.

Importantly, the integration of modelling tools will facilitate an integration of perspective at the higher level of decision-making. It will provide insights into why long-term strategies in the domains of infrastructure, energy, land use and water supply may need to be integrated for the purposes of increasing resilience to climatic changes. It will then deliver indications on what aspects need to be considered for coherent and resilient planning at national scale. This in turn will suggest why and how resilience topics can be integrated into CCG offers to partner countries.

The remaining of the document is structured as follows: Section 1.2 presents the key definitions of resilience aspects included in this document, Section 2 presents the CCG modelling offer, identifies their contributions to resilience and maps how the models may be interlinked and used to answer policy questions, Section 3 presents the gaps identified in the models and the limitations of linking models, Section 4 discusses the contributions of this document to CCG work and, finally, Section 5 shows opportunities for future work.

1.2. Definitions

The term 'resilience' is broadly understood. However, specific definitions can be used to differentiate between aspects of resilience that affect the practical application of the concept. Such definitions are presented in this section.

- **Resilience of energy systems:** The long-term resilience of the energy supply mix to climatic changes means the system's ability to adapt and differentiate the energy supply matrix as service demands and the availability of resources (e.g. water for hydropower or water for cooling thermal power plants) evolve due to climatic changes. As well as adapting to long-term climatic changes, energy infrastructure should be able to maintain security of supply coping with day-to-day operational challenges and when there are extreme weather events.
- **Resilience of infrastructure:** Infrastructure must be able to withstand climate shocks. This includes built infrastructure such as roads, bridges, dams, commercial and domestic buildings, among others. The infrastructure must be built to a level that satisfies constraints related to expected shocks in a given area or type of system.
- **Resilience of agricultural practices:** Agricultural practices can be improved to adapt to changing (e.g. decreasing) average precipitation. Options include investments in increased mechanisation which in turn allow increased yields and decreased reliance on rainwater. Where possible, non-climate-resilient crops can be gradually substituted by more resilient crops. Practices of re-forestation, or increase in protected areas, or limitation in the rates of land use changes can also be included.
- **Resilience of water supply:** Water supply system must be resilient to water shortages (e.g. due to decreasing precipitation patterns or prolonged droughts). Options to improve this may include investments in desalination facilities, where there is access to the sea and in cases shortage of groundwater. The resilience of water supply is not only given by the existence of water desalination capacity, but also by the availability of energy to feed the desalination plants (e.g. electricity to feed reverse osmosis processes). Solutions for wastewater treatment are also considered.
- **Resilience of supply chains, trade, and industrial capacity:** The required flow of materials that supply the built environment, energy systems and food systems must be secured, and their contributions to climate change minimised. This involves exploring how trade and industrial capacity must be designed given geographical, local capacity and demand constraints.
- **Resilience of governance:** Systems for decision making around energy systems and wider development issues must themselves be resilient to shocks – political, social and economic – in order to support just transitions for CCG.
- **Resilience of transition pathways:** Transition pathways should be designed such that they avoid over reliance on contentious elements, which could include new/speculative technologies, particular governments gaining or staying in power, or major behaviour change. Co-creation of transition pathway with the people most affected may increase its chance of successful implementation.

2. CCG modelling tools and their contribution to resilience research

Figure 1 gives a high-level overview of the coverage of CCG's modelling toolkit, already hinting at the resilience aspects included. Each theme includes coloured dots that refer to models and their inclusion of each given theme, the models are MUSE, CLEWs, NISMOD, OSeMOSYS, MAT-dp and FlexTool. The categories on the left of the figure are inspired by the energy conversion stages including passive systems, conversion devices and end-uses drawn by Cullen and Allwood [11] in their Sankey diagram, while the final category 'Supply and demand balances and impacts' refers to the effects of the transformations on the economy and other systems.

While energy resources are central to the modelling toolkit, other biophysical and resource systems are included, since they are critical also for energy planners. These include material resources, land uses, water system and the climate system. The resources coming from these systems are converted into useful commodities and conveyed towards end uses through different types of infrastructure. The CCG toolkit shown covers energy and transport infrastructure, but it should be noted that the list of transport topics is not inclusive of all the transport models used in CCG. Those will be included in future work.

In the CCG modelling offer, the end uses of commodities include quantifying the availability of commodities (e.g. food and water) subject to changes in energy and transport services. Aspects of particular concern on the end use side are supply and demand balances, asset exposure, vulnerability and risk.

Climate change is affecting the different biophysical and resource systems, infrastructure and the end uses simultaneously. Therefore, resilience must be considered at all the levels shown in Figure 1. Often, effects at one level or on one system cascade onto others, e.g., Sridharan et al [12]. The links between levels and across domains can be represented through links between modelling tools that assess each of the systems separately. The rest of this section

is structured as follows: the modelling tools are first described, then the way each incorporates aspects of resilience is detailed, and finally, the potential links between the tools are illustrated.

Figure 1 Coverage of CCG Toolkit with respect to resilience.

2.1. Description of the modelling tools

OSeMOSYS: The Open Source energy Modelling System finds the configuration of the energy system (in terms of investments and operation) that minimizes the net present cost of the whole system across the time domain of the study while meeting energy demands and several other technology, policy and resource constraints. A model generated in OSeMOSYS can include the whole energy system (i.e. primary resources, the power system, refineries, and detailed representation of end use sectors such as transport, residential and industry) or be limited to a subset of this (e.g. the power system only). The model represents reality as a network of ‘technologies’ and ‘commodities’. Technologies are essentially boxes with inputs, outputs, and a transfer function between them. Commodities are what flows between technologies. The optimisation is normally based on least-cost criteria, but the objective function can also be changed. The time domain of OSeMOSYS models is typically the one of strategic planning decisions, i.e. several decades. The time resolution is customisable according to the purpose of the analysis. It can be high if more operational details for the energy sector are needed. Most models represent a country as just a few regions at most in order to make the analysis manageable.

FlexTool: Is a power sector dispatch model. Its primary focus is to analyse the flexibility of power systems based on national capacity investment plans and forecasts. FlexTool can model hourly timesteps, or less, to model the real-world challenges of a power system with high proportions of intermittent renewable energy supplies. It provides a least-cost optimisation of the generation mix, along with flexibility solutions for grids, storage, demand-side response and sector coupling.

MUSE: The ModUlar energy System Environment (MUSE) is a whole systems energy model which focuses on the development of long-term transitions. Its scope is thus similar to OSeMOSYS. However, MUSE is an agent-based model which is a simulation of how investors and consumers behave within an energy system. This enables MUSE to relax assumptions such as perfect foresight and allows for emergent properties to develop. For example, investors do not have prior knowledge of future energy prices or demand and must make their decisions under uncertainty, much like in the real world. The model solves a model clearing algorithm for multiple representative timesteps per milestone years up to 2050 and beyond.

NISMOD: The National Infrastructure Systems MODEL (NISMOD) is a detailed spatial network risk analysis model that (1) represents infrastructure assets and their connectivity; (2) does extensive stress testing of networks by intersecting them with spatial probabilistic hazards; and (3) quantifies the vulnerability and risk outcomes in terms of damages and losses to assets, people and the economy.

MAT-dp: The Material Demand Projections (MAT-dp) model uses projections of electricity generation and combines them with LCA of different technologies involved in the electricity system to obtain normalised amounts of materials for each type of technology. MAT-dp can then determine the amounts of materials required for national electricity systems and their projected changes, as well as their embodied emissions. MAT-dp was created with the aim of showing the effect of embodied emissions on energy systems, so that they can be included in emission reduction plans, thereby achieving higher savings than only focusing on direct emissions. The results obtained using MAT-dp may be used to plan industrial capacity and resource trade to ensure the projected materials required in energy systems are available. The results may also be used to plan carbon budgets in a more holistic manner, since embodied emissions are included.

CLEWs: The Climate, Land use, Energy, Water systems (CLEWs) framework is not a tool per se, but rather a modelling approach to analyse quantitatively the links between biophysical systems and how these links affect the impacts each system has on the others. One of the ways of analysing these links is using the OSeMOSYS tool. This is the way chosen within CCG. By using the OSeMOSYS tool, we can carry out a simultaneous optimisation of investments and resource uses across the land use, water and energy domains, in the long range. With the generic object-based representation of the system typical of OSeMOSYS (I.e. based on generic Technologies and Commodities), anything can be represented in a model, from a power plant to a piece of land or a water processing technology. A CLEWs model in OSeMOSYS can therefore be built starting from an energy model and then adding land uses and water supply chain like blocks in a Lego construction. The time domain of CLEWs models is, like the one of OSeSMOYS models focussing on energy, typically the one of strategic planning decisions, i.e. several decades (e.g. well beyond 2050 if we want to capture climatic changes). The time resolution is customisable according to the purpose of the analysis. There is usually no spatially explicit representation of energy and water infrastructure.

2.2. Resilience aspects covered by the modelling tools

The models include aspects of resilience, specifically:

CLEWs (and OSeMOSYS within it): It can incorporate aspects of resilience of energy infrastructure, agricultural practices and water supply. Regarding energy infrastructure, it can introduce exogenous inputs (taking from outputs of other models, with a soft-linking approach) on unplanned downtime of technologies such as thermal power plants, solar PV fields, wind turbines, and the T&D network. The latter cannot be represented branch by branch, but parts of it can be represented, as aggregated capacity in one region. Exogenous inputs can also be introduced, on variation of efficiency due to e.g. variation of water availability or water temperature for cooling of thermal power plants. Also the variation of availability of hydro power due to varying water flows can be considered (and with it mitigating measures such as variation of the operation of dam infrastructure). Changes in the availability of primary resources fed to the power plants can be considered, which in turn cascade into changes in the operation of power plants (or even shutting down, becoming stranded).

Regarding the agricultural practices, changes in practices for different crops can be modelled (e.g. modernisation and increase of mechanisation, with consequent increased use of fertilisers, energy and irrigation water and decreased use of rainwater). An improvement in practices translates in higher yields and less resilience on rainwater. The introduction of more resilient crops at the expense of less resilient ones can be introduced, or the change in trade of food products. Regarding the water supply, varying precipitation patterns can be modelled, which in turn affect the availability of water for public supply, energy sector and land uses, and force changes in each of the sectors to reduce needs.

Resilience can also be modelled by thinking through specific scenarios. The modeller may create 'no-adaptation' scenarios, where s(he) locks the infrastructure investments for future years to what they would be if climate changes were not taken into account, and sees what the actual supply-demand balance ends up looking like in case the climatic changes happen. It might result into unserved demand (we can represent unserved demand). CELWS examines the resilience of a nexus system in relation to long-term changes to climate - i.e. it is relevant for long-term planning.

MAT-dp: The resilience of supply chains is analysed by quantifying the amounts of bulk and critical materials required for projected electricity systems and identifying how they will be provided at a national level. Required changes in material supply as renewables are taken up can be identified to inform strategies on shifting industrial capacity to accommodate any new or changing demand. Trade strategies for materials that cannot be produced locally can also be informed. The embodied emissions produced by the projected systems are quantified by MAT-dp to help identify the materials with the highest mass and embodied emissions for including them in emission reduction strategies.

NISMOD: Its risk and resilience analysis specifically looks at the spatial vulnerabilities, risks and resilience of infrastructure networks to extreme hazard shocks. It quantifies risks in terms of the direct damages to asset exposed to hazards of given magnitudes and probabilities, and indirect losses in terms of the service disruptions due to asset failures and the resulting economic impacts of such disruptions. Outcomes of such an analysis inform on where the network vulnerabilities are concentrated and how we can improve network resilience by strengthening the locations with the highest vulnerabilities. The tool looks at asset and system level improvement options, such as improving the design standards of assets to make them more climate resilient or adding more network linkages (e.g., backup supply of

electricity or multi-modal routes of connectivity in the case of transport networks) to maintain continuity of service. Quantifying such options and their effects in reducing risks helps create an understanding of the effectiveness of network resilience options. Options can also be prioritised, in terms of understanding their costs and the benefits of risks reduction that they provide.

MUSE: The resilience aspects covered by MUSE are somewhat similar to OSeMOSYS as far as the energy system is concerned. However, the peculiarity of MUSE is modelling resilience in energy systems by incorporating the behaviour of investors and consumers. This allows the model to anticipate what would happen if shocks on energy prices or demand were to occur.

FlexTool: The key resilience feature of the tool is given by its name, as it allows for flexibility to be incorporated to energy system models. FlexTool may find how to expand energy capacity in a relatively small time-frame (one year), finding the most suitable flexibility solutions for a specific power system. FlexTool applies stresses to the modelled energy system and determines ways for it to be more flexible. This is showcased at an operational level, e.g., considering variable power generation or high gas prices, and in investment in new assets to cope with supply risks, always finding an optimised low-cost solution.

2.3. Linking CCG models

Bringing CCG work together to create more robust analyses that include resilience required the following interdisciplinary work by the authoring team:

1. With several exchanges, we created a common understanding of the inputs and outputs of each model;
2. We created a common understanding of the spatial and temporal scales of models;
3. One of the key aspects of risk and resilience analysis is the stress testing of models, which means simulating potentially a very large ensemble of failure scenarios is estimating the impacts repeatedly. We created a preliminary understanding of how the models can be computationally scaled to be able to do such failure ensemble analysis is important;
4. We worked out a mapping of the potential linkages between the models, which would serve the aim to provide a comprehensive representation of resilience.

A description and representation of the potential links between the modelling tools as devised in our analysis is given below, presenting the links by pairs of models. The Annex of this document contains diagrams created to link each of the models, which informed the links presented in this section.

OSeMOSYS within CLEWs

CLEWs is a modelling approach and, within CCG, it uses OSeMOSYS as a modelling tool. In a CLEWs model that uses OSeMOSYS, the energy, land use and water system and the links between them are represented and optimised jointly. In this sense, an energy system model in OSeMOSYS can be seen as one block of a CLEWs model, to which blocks related to land uses and water supply are linked, like in a Lego structure. This provides an opportunity for the in-country work: when energy system models are built with OSeMOSYS in collaboration with energy experts from the countries, they can be then expanded adding elements of land use and water use by involving the relevant sector experts.

FlexTool link with OSeMOSYS and CLEWs

CLEWs can link to FlexTool via OSeMOSYS in a linear process. That is, CLEWs generates a system which takes into account the climate, land-use, energy and water systems and FlexTool analyses the power system to see whether it contains enough flexibility. FlexTool can be used to 'validate' the generation mix calculated in OSeMOSYS.

NISMOD link with OSeMOSYS and CLEWs

NISMOD is a very spatially disaggregated model that represents a system in terms of the locations of point assets and their connectivity through physical line assets. For example, an electricity network representation in NISMOD would include identifying the locations of the power plants, substations and their connecting transmission lines. On the other hand, OSeMOSYS/CLEWs (and the electricity system representation within them) are not spatially explicit. The generating and the transmission and distribution infrastructure are aggregated by capacity, with no information on the location. Therefore, one link between NISMOD and OSeMOSYS/CLEWs could consist of NISMOD assessing in a spatially explicit way risks associated with the least-cost commodity (and especially electricity) supply mix proposed by OSeMOSYS/CLEWs. In the first step of this iteration, OSeMOSYS/CLEWs could feed demand and load profiles, the supply mix, and the energy consumption profiles to the NISMOD network usage attributes. NISMOD could feed back to

OSeMOSYS/CLEWs infrastructure constraints to be taken into account for the purposes of obtaining climate-resilient infrastructure.

The results of such a combination of tools could inform CCG partners and final users of the models on the risks associated with long-term infrastructure investments made with an integrated planning perspective, thereby significantly enriching the traditional OSeMOSYS/CLEWs assessments. Inputs and outputs must be aggregated up from NISMOD to feed into OSeMOSYS/CLEWs or disaggregated down from OSeMOSYS/CLEWs to feed into NISMOD.

NISMOD Link with FlexTool

FlexTool is designed to analyse the power plant level attributes such as load, capacity, and energy requirements. This could feed into NISMOD geospatial information on power plants which are connected to the rest of the electricity network structure. Hence the main input from FlexTool would be to provide information to NISMOD on the power plant supply attributes.

NISMOD Link with MAT-dp

The main link between the two models is the consideration of the different technologies in an energy or transport system. However, NISMOD and MAT-dp work at different levels, where NISMOD has a higher geographical resolution and MAT-dp does an analysis at country level, without including spatial considerations. This spatial aspect has potential for future interactions, since identifying the sources of production and linking them to demand centres would strengthen MAT-dp's conclusions on trade and local production. In turn, MAT-dp considers materials in detail, which can then be fed into NISMOD in the form of material scarcity. This can be used as a risk factor for NISMOD's predictions. NISMOD can identify infrastructure risks, which could be combined with cost and material implications of replacing technologies from MAT-dp to obtain more detailed estimations of the carbon costs of replacing infrastructure.

MUSE Link with NISMOD

MUSE provides long-term, aggregated energy scenarios of how the future may develop. Whereas NISMOD works on a more disaggregated scale is able to quantify the likelihood of vulnerability and risk outcomes. NISMOD can help inform MUSE with downtime and maintenance required for a particular energy system based on particular regions.

MUSE Link with OSeMOSYS and CLEWs

MUSE and OSeMOSYS are complimentary models with similar inputs and outputs. However, the underlying methodologies are different. Where OSeMOSYS takes the perspective of a social planner (with the objective of minimising the overall system cost over a long time period while respecting regulatory and resource constraints) MUSE takes the perspective of different agents. These models are complimentary and can provide different outputs based on the underlying assumptions to broaden the range of quantitative advice provided to policy makers.

Since the logic of CLEWs within CCG is the same as the logic of OSeMOSYS, the perspective represented by a CLEWs analysis is the same as that of an OSeMOSYS analysis, just extended also to land use and water supply planning. MUSE can be expanded to the water supply and land use sectors, to see how these systems may interact from the perspective of the agents involved. This could strengthen significantly the insights given by the models, extending the wide range of policy advice already given by the couple MUSE-OSeMOSYS also to policy coherence across climate, land, energy and water.

MAT-dp Link with OSeMOSYS and CLEWs

The main link between MAT-dp and OSeMOSYS (whether used for energy or CLEWs modelling) is their consideration of electricity systems. Both models study how electricity system changes over time will have impacts for other systems, such as primary energy sources, land, water, or construction materials. The key intersection is the current and future electricity power plant capacities, split by type of technology. These are the output of a least-cost optimisation in OSeMOSYS/CLEWs and an input for MAT-dp. Both models make assumptions regarding the aggregated type of power plant so when linking these models together, the inputs of OSeMOSYS/CLEWs regarding power plants need to be shared with MAT-dp and considered with the same level of aggregation. In an OSeMOSYS model, often the types of power plants are highly aggregated (to balance detail with computational requirements of the model). However, the aggregation level can be customised. In the extreme case, individual power plants can also be represented. MAT-dp may need quite disaggregated information on the types of power plants. Therefore, the inputs of OSeMOSYS/CLEWs will need to be calibrated on the level of aggregation needed by MAT-dp and then they will need to be shared with the latter.

The combination of OSeMOSYS/CLEWs and MAT-dp can be the first step in the analysis of a climate, land use, energy, water and materials nexus. In this instance, given the focus of MAT-dp on the electricity system, it will provide a more comprehensive picture of the construction and operation phases of electricity systems. Users of this combination of

models might obtain clearer insights on the needs for investment, trade, industrial capacity, resource use and environmental impact of any proposed modification to their electricity system.

MAT-dp Link with MUSE

MUSE’s outputs are similar to OSeMOSYS and CLEWs, since they all project long-term energy system changes. Therefore, the link between MAT-dp and MUSE is similar in nature to the one between MAT-dp and OSeMOSYS or CLEWs. MAT-dp can share information on the embodied emissions that the proposed energy systems would have, with an option to feed those back to the MUSE and check if any technology parameters need to be adjusted. Similarly, risks of material supply or increasing uncertainty of material costs can be fed to MUSE to obtain results on energy systems with lower supply chain risks.

MAT-dp Link with FlexTool

There is no immediate link between FlexTool and MAT-dp, since the time involved in the modelling is short-term or dynamic for FlexTool and long-term for MAT-dp. Yet, linking MUSE, FlexTool and MAT-dp could bring benefits for exploring several types of risks, e.g., short-term disruptions and material scarcity.

2.4 Answering policy questions combining models

Linking some of the CCG models would provide users and modellers with the ability to answer additional questions. Table 1 summarises the policy-relevant questions from linking tools.

Table 1 Policy-relevant questions potentially covered by the linked tools.

Model combination	Policy-relevant questions
FlexTool with OSeMOSYS and CLEWs	This combination could be used to perform long-term planning of a full energy system, taking into account high time resolution operational issues of the power system, in particular for systems with a high portion of weather-dependent renewables, under scenarios of climate change impacts.
MUSE with OSeMOSYS and CLEWs	This could provide insights on climate compatible growth strategies in the energy system (and potentially the land and water systems) both from the perspective of a social planner and from the perspective of the various involved agents.
OSeMOSYS within CLEWs	This can indicate to policy makers cost-optimal long-term investment strategies for the energy sector that are coherent with those of land and water uses and take into account long-term climate change impacts on natural resources.
Mat-dp with OSeMOSYS and CLEWs	This combination could provide recommendations for policy makers on coherent strategies across the Climate, Land, Energy and Water domains and the implications for material resource uses (all of high relevance for the updates of Nationally Determined Contributions).
NISMOD and MAT-dp	These models could be used to inform how climate risks to infrastructure network impact the supply chains of different types of materials, which then has an impact on the critical supplies of energy resources.
NISMOD and CLEWs, MUSE, OSeMOSYS, Flextool	The models in combination could be used to understand how long-term planning objectives might be affected by infrastructure risks. For example, if the existing and planned power plants that are identified as most value to long-term energy provisions in a country or region might be at risk due to climate hazards then we can better understand how these risks could be reduced.

2.5 Timeline of identified model changes and additional development

During the conversations identifying model interactions, several follow-up activities related to changes to be made in models or additional model development to incorporate extra functionalities were captured. Table 2 summarises such activities and classifies them based on the time they may take to implement and whether the changes are related to modelling, non-modelling or a combined model application.

Table 2 Timeline of model changes identified in the model interactions and additional model development needed.

Type of change	Short-term (1-6 months)	Medium-term (6-12 months)	Long-term (>1 year)
Modelling	CLEWs and MAT-dp: Share CO ₂ emissions, direct from CLEWs and embodied from MAT-dp for	NISMOD and MAT-dp: Share sources of production and add material demand centres.	MUSE and MAT-dp to look at long-term scenarios and how they can be achieved with

	<p>deciding long-term strategies that include electricity generation technologies and the risks of material scarcity and trade.</p> <p>Comparing MUSE and OSeMOSYS results with FlexTool.</p> <p>NISMOD - Resilience model - and other models: Understanding and linking the input-outputs from other models in terms of spatial and temporal scales.</p>	<p>MUSE (or CLEWs/OSeMOSYS) and MAT-dp: Share electricity output from MUSE and feed it to MAT-dp to optimise for resources and feed insights on material-intensive technologies back to MUSE. See if the results change.</p> <p>NISMOD - Resilience model - and other models: Developing a prototype code/process-flow to build a demonstrable example showing data inputs and outputs.</p> <p>NISMOD - Resilience model - and MAT-dp: Developing a possible extension for transport networks and commodity flows along networks to connect to material flows of MAT-dp.</p> <p>MUSE and CLEWs: analysis of complementarity of aspects represented/ impacts of the different approaches.</p> <p>MUSE and NISMOD: assessing the short-term risks of different energy systems with different geographical make-ups.</p>	<p>limited resources in different regions.</p> <p>MUSE, FlexTool and MAT-dp: Analyse short- and long-term risks for energy demand and material scarcity.</p> <p>NISMOD and MAT-dp: Share spatially-disaggregated data to include transmission and distribution in both models.</p> <p>NISMOD - Resilience model - and other models: Implementing for case study countries.</p> <p>Increasing the complementarity between tools, e.g. extending domain of MUSE to land and water.</p>
Non-modelling	<p>Include insights of non-modellers on resilience and its key aspects in the energy, transport, and resource use planning domain.</p> <p>Workshop session with non-modellers to brainstorm resilience research questions and how they could be addressed with models.</p> <p>Discussion on how issues of wider economic-social vulnerability/resilience might feed into or affect the scenarios that we model e.g. political unrest, corruption, weak governance etc - how they might affect the model drivers or how the models could contribute to resilience planning.</p>	<p>Implement some non-modellers brainstorming session questions in the relevant models.</p>	<p>Contribute to wider resilience planning.</p>
Model application	<p>Harmonising inputs for one selected common application (e.g., Kenya and/or Lao).</p>	<p>First-order soft-linked modelling exercise for one selected application (e.g., Kenya or Lao), highlighting complementarity.</p>	<p>Finding additional case study for implementation.</p>

3. Gaps and limitations

Gaps of the models included in this document

While several elements of resilience can be examined with the models currently used in CCG programme, some gaps remain.

First, most of the tools are not well-suited to study acute or short term events, e.g., as seconds or minutes of fluctuations in electricity generation, flash floods, sudden price changes or extreme weather events. This is because most models assume a certain set of conditions in a country, e.g. that certain hydropower electricity capacity being deployed, without evaluating whether there may be rapid changes in such parameters. In the hydro example, a drought, political conflict, or government decision may impact the capacity, but these factors are not assessed in the models, mainly given their uncertainty. Two models stand out in being able to cope with some degree of shocks: FlexTool and NISMOD. FlexTool has the ability to look at short-term shocks on the power system. This is because FlexTool is designed to look at a single year of a power system. Thus leading to improved understanding of the short-term effects of a political conflict or government decision. In turn, the NISMOD framework represents the systems at detailed network level and quantifies short term shock impacts, for example, post flood damages and losses to electricity assets and networks. NISMOD provides the potential linkage for disaggregating the outputs of the different high-level models (CLEWs, MUSE, OSeMOSYS-energy, FlexTool) and seeing how long-term planning objectives might be affected by localised shock events.

Another gap in many these models is the lack of geographical data to sufficiently represent the systems realistically, especially if we aim to integrate them at different scales. As we go from a high-level representation on an energy system (example at the national scale) to the asset level representation of the network, we might not have location-specific information on assets and their connectivity across a system. Hence, there might be a top-down error in allocating more (or less) supply or demand to locations based on using a smaller set of asset than what might be available in a country. This has implications on quantifying and predicting risk outcomes, where some critical assets might not be identified or some assets might be identified as being more critical than what they actually might be.

Limitations

Computational simplifications are a limitation that should be acknowledged in any joint analysis. For instance, with a methodology of broad scope such as CLEWs (which encompasses the Climate, Land, Energy and Water systems), several characteristics of each system need to be simplified (for computational reasons and because data is not always available). This introduces errors that, in turn, can propagate to other tools, if they are linked to CLEWs. E.g, a CLEWs model may identify the hydro power infrastructure that could be needed to meet demands for energy and agricultural water in a region, while providing also flood-protection services. This information can, in turn, be used by MAT-dp to calculate material demands, or by NISMOD to assess the infrastructure risks in the specific region and scenario. However, the results of CLEWs depend on a number of hardly collectable assumptions, such as the operational rules of the water storages, projected climatic changes, structure of the rest of the energy system, patterns of use of agricultural water, among others.

Finally, by showcasing the way CCG models may interact, we strive to identify useful inputs and outputs that may be shared. However, we acknowledge that these models can at best communicate by sharing such inputs and outputs, but they are not intrinsically linked to be run in parallel with each other.

4. Contributions to the work done by CCG

The analysis of the aspects of resilience that the CCG modelling tools can cover is meant to service the national partnership work. Where questions of resilience arise in the national partnership work, the local partners may refer to the maps we created and see what aspects are covered by the currently available toolkit and what aspects can be captured in addition. The additional aspects can be captured by 'plugging in' new tools, like in a 'Lego' structure. When such need for additional insights is identified, WS4 shall provide the research infrastructure and workflows to make the additions possible and shall showcase results through test applications.

In parallel with the collaboration with the national partnerships, and the provision of services outlined above, the WS4-Resilience team shall work on longer-term model development aspects. These aim to make the representation of resilience aspects more comprehensive and cohesive within the CCG modelling toolkit. One example is the suggestion of analysing the complementarity of MUSE and CLEWs around the representation of transition pathways towards resilient energy and resource use planning (conditional to availability of funding).

Contribution to non-modelling CCG activities can also be done using the material produced in this Resilience sprint. Namely, WS5a focuses on policies to support inclusive transitions to climate compatible growth. It has two

interconnected priority projects. The first focuses on political economy and aims to understand decision-making contexts, policy and programme implementation, and the distributional impacts of decisions and implementation. The second focuses on the co-creation of scenarios and pathways towards inclusive and climate compatible growth. Both of these projects can help build our understandings of resilience, particularly as they relate to how different stakeholders in CCG partner countries understand, drive and undermine resilience. This may include more resilient governance and policy mixes, knowledge sharing, and the co-development of (climate) resilient futures.

Benefitting partner countries is one of the ultimate aims of the work done by the CCG programme. As such, partner countries must be consulted regarding their resilience needs. This can help identify what CCG can offer associated to the links between the different tools that have been identified through this document. The aim is to not constraint the country needs and vision, but rather co-create solutions based on the country needs.

5. Future work

The work done for this document included many energy topics and only few transport topics. Thus, the next iteration of this work needs to evaluate in more detail the resilience topics in the transport modelling offer of CCG. This should further elucidate shocks affecting transport systems and how those can be studied using CCG models.

Future work can include more links with ongoing work in CCG, specifically the sprint on designing mixed methods approaches to developing scenarios and pathways towards inclusive CCG.

A workshop with qualitative and mixed-methods researchers could be conducted to discuss their concerns and research questions on resilience topics, and how they could be addressed with CCG models or model combinations. Concerns and questions could include how issues of wider economic-social vulnerability/resilience might feed into or affect the scenarios that we model, e.g. political unrest, corruption, or weak governance, how these issues might affect the model drivers or finding additional resilience planning questions that the models may be able to answer.

Future work may also deploy a selection of the links between the models showcased above (to the extent made possible by the resource allocation and time) in the national modelling work in Kenya. All the partners involved in this sprint are already working with the National Partnerships to set up modelling activities in Kenya. Harmonising input assumptions and selectively linking tools will be a low-effort step that all can take and that will greatly benefit the individual modelling activities. It will also significantly increase the quality and validity of the outputs and it will pave the road for similar efforts in the other partner countries.

Additional topics identified during the discussions with the authors of this report led to identifying the following topic that CCG as a whole may incorporate in the future: geospatial socio-economic analysis, including analysis of trends of urbanisation, population growth, changes in the demands for services and related elasticity to prices.

CRedit author statement

Karla Cervantes Barron: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualisation, Supervision; **Francesco Gardumi:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualisation; **Raghav Pant:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualisation; **Jennifer Cronin:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualisation; **Julia Tomei:** Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing; **Alex Kell:** Investigation, Visualisation; **Jonathan M Cullen:** Writing - Review & Editing

References

- [1] National Infrastructure Commission, "Anticipate, react, recover- Resilient Infrastructure Systems," 2020.
- [2] F. Gardumi *et al.*, "From the development of an open-source energy modelling tool to its application and the creation of communities of practice: The example of OSeMOSYS," *Energy Strategy Reviews*, vol. 20, pp. 209–228, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.esr.2018.03.005.
- [3] T. Niet, A. Shivakumar, F. Gardumi, W. Usher, E. Williams, and M. Howells, "Developing a community of practice around an open source energy modelling tool," *Energy Strategy Reviews*, vol. 35, May 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.esr.2021.100650.
- [4] M. Howells *et al.*, "OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System. An introduction to its ethos, structure and development.," *Energy Policy*, vol. 39, no. 10, pp. 5850–5870, Oct. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.033.
- [5] International Renewable Energy Agency, *Power system flexibility for the energy transition, Part 2: IRENA FlexTool methodology*. Abu Dhabi, 2018. [Online]. Available: www.irena.org
- [6] I. García Kerdan, S. Giarola, and A. Hawkes, "A novel energy systems model to explore the role of land use and reforestation in achieving carbon mitigation targets: A Brazil case study," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 232, pp. 796–821, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.05.345.
- [7] J. Sachs, Y. Meng, S. Giarola, and A. Hawkes, "An agent-based model for energy investment decisions in the residential sector," *Energy*, vol. 172, pp. 752–768, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2019.01.161.
- [8] S. Thacker, R. Pant, and J. W. Hall, "System-of-systems formulation and disruption analysis for multi-scale critical national infrastructures," *Reliability Engineering and System Safety*, vol. 167, no. April, pp. 30–41, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.ress.2017.04.023.
- [9] K. Cervantes Barron, M. E. Hakker, and J. M. Cullen, "Future low-carbon electricity in Africa: how much material is needed?," 2021, doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-1160025/v1.
- [10] E. P. Ramos *et al.*, "The climate, land, energy, and water systems (CLEWs) framework: A retrospective of activities and advances to 2019," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 16, no. 3, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/abd34f.
- [11] J. M. Cullen and J. M. Allwood, "Theoretical efficiency limits for energy conversion devices," *Energy*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 2059–2069, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2010.01.024.
- [12] V. Sridharan *et al.*, "Resilience of the Eastern African electricity sector to climate driven changes in hydropower generation," *Nature Communications*, vol. 10, no. 1, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41467-018-08275-7.

Appendix

Model interaction diagrams

NISMOD Link with OSeMOSYS and CLEWs

CLEWs - KTH and NISMOD - Oxford

NISMOD Link with MAT-dp

NISMOD - Oxford and MAT-dp Cam

MUSE Link with NISMOD

NISMOD - Oxford and MUSE - Imperial

MUSE Link with OSeMOSYS and CLEws

MUSE- Imperial and CLEWS - KTH

MUSE parts in red miro

MAT-dp Link with OSeMOSYS and Clews

CLEWS - KTH and MAT-dp -Cambridge

MAT-dp Link with MUSE

MAT-dp -Cambridge and MUSE - Imperial

MAT-dp Link with FlexTool

MAT-dp -Cambridge and Flextool - Imperial

